

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF IMPACT DAMAGE DETECTION FOR CFRP STRUCTURES BY LAMB WAVE SENSING USING FBG/PZT HYBRID SYSTEM

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Abstract

Investigations for impact detection, namely identification of location and energy level of an impact have been conducted using novel damage detection system that is developed for composite materials using AWG-type filter and FBG sensors. This system can detect the damage occurring / growing by detecting an elastic wave launched from a PZT element using FBG optical fiber sensors.

In order to detect the waves generated by impacts, specimens of CFRP panels embedded and patched FBG sensors and PZT actuators were prepared. Impact loading tests were carried out by hammer hitting and using drop-weight-type impact machine.

As the results of the impact loading tests, it was confirmed that the waves generated by impacts could be detected successfully by the system. Moreover possibility of identification of the location and energy level of the impact by detecting and analyzing the waves generated by it was confirmed through the experiments.

1 Introduction

In recent years, composite material has been widely applied to not only secondary structures but also primary structures of aircraft [1] because of its advantages of high specific strength ratio, high specific modulus ratio, good corrosion resistance and low cost manufacturing. The application of composite materials for the fuselage of a business jet has been confirmed as a success story.

Damages of aircrafts are caused by not only mechanical loading during flight or taxiing but also

several types of impacts such as bird or hail strike, dropping of tools and crash of cargos. And the fracture behavior of composite material is still considerably complicated. That of CFRP, which has laminate constructions, is considered as complicated combinations in some fracture modes such as fracture of matrix, peeling of fibers from matrix, delamination, fracture of fibers, and so on. Accordingly, prediction of damage growth and residual lifetime of CFRP structural parts is so difficult differing from metals. Therefore, when CFRP is applied to the structural material of aircraft, if any damages exist, it guarantees safety by preventing these damages from occurring and growing (No Damage Growth Design) [2]. In some cases, the design allowable of CFRP is decided based on CAI strength and this value is thought to be corresponding to about 25 % of fracture strength of CFRP [3]. Therefore, in order to introduce the Damage Tolerance Design, which is now applied to metal structures, to composite structures, clear understanding about damage initiation and growth mechanism is absolutely needed. That is why research and development of structural health monitoring have been conducted for several decades all over the world. Recently, we proposed novel structural health monitoring system, where a PZT element functions as the actuator for elastic wave excitation while an FBG optical fiber works as the sensor (receiver). This system was successfully detected the damage propagation in CFRP structures. Therefore if detection of impacts, which are one of the reasons to generate damages in composite structures, could be possible, the useful understanding of fracture behavior of composite materials is obtained and consequently the Damage

Tolerance Design will be applied to the composite structures near future.

In this study, in order to evaluate the feasibility of impact detection using the same device construction as in the case of damage detection system that we proposed, demonstration and evaluation whether waves generated by impacts could be detected by the device construction was conducted.

2 Damage monitoring system

Recently, we proposed novel structural health monitoring system [4–6], where a PZT element functions as the actuator for elastic wave excitation while an FBG optical fiber works as the sensor (receiver). Although Commercial FBG sensor systems are capable of detecting elastic waves with a frequency of several dozen kHz, their capability for damage detection is not satisfactory. In order to get higher sensitivity than commercial FBG sensor systems, the AWG-type filter was adopted to the system. Figure 1 shows the configuration of the AWG-type filter. As a result, the structural health monitoring system has got high sensitivity to the displacements in the FBG gratings with microvibrations from strains due to an elastic wave launched from the PZT elements. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the basic damage monitoring system. The damage detection principle of this system is based on the energy change of the received waveform. If a damaged section exists in the path of the elastic wave, the energy of the elastic wave will change. By detecting this change, the system can

Figure 1. Configuration of the AWG-type filter and schematic image of FBG reflection spectrum

detect the damage in a composite structure. We could successfully detect the damage propagation by this system. Figure 3 shows an application image of the damage monitoring system for an inaccessible critical region (hot spot) in a wing box structure in

which the FBG sensor and PZT actuator are positioned.

Figure 2. Schematic overview of basic damage monitoring system

Figure 3. Damage monitoring system for the wing box structure

3 Experimental procedures

3.1 Impact detection with flat panels

Figure 4 shows the configuration of the test specimen for impact detection with flat panels. The specimen is a quasi-isotropic laminate of 16 ply ($[45/0/-45/90]_{2S}$), which simulates the wing skin of an aircraft. A FBG optical fiber sensor and a PZT actuator were bonded to the specimen surface for impact and impact damage detection.

Figure 4. Configuration of the test specimens for impact detection of flat panels

We conducted the impact detection test using a drop-weight-type impact machine. The weight was 10 pounds and its tip was a hemisphere having a diameter of 15.75 mm. The specimen was located on the aluminum base (thickness: 20 mm) and was impacted at energies ranging from 3.3 J to 26.4 J. The waves generated by the impact were received using the FBG sensor and the AWG-type filter of the damage monitoring system, as the FBG sensor can receive the lamb waves generated by the PZT actuator. The damage generated by impact was also detected using the FBG/PZT damage monitoring system that we proposed. Furthermore, ultrasonic inspection (C-scan) was carried out for measuring the size of the impact damage.

Four consecutive channels of the AWG-type filter were selected for impact detection. Channel 1 is adjacent to the FBG reflection spectrum and channel 2 is adjacent to channel 1 (see Fig. 1). Before impact, the FBG reflection spectrum was positioned at the center between the two filters by means of thermal controlling.

3.2 Impact detection with structural elements

We prepared structural element test specimens that simulated the skin/stringer bonding parts of an aircraft structure, as shown in Figure 5. The specimen consisted of a CFRP skin/stringer structure with quasi-isotropic laminate. Impact loading was carried out by hammer hitting on the static without any forced restriction. However, the impact load was not assigned a specific damage level. Further, the impact load was located on the opposite side of the bonded stringer surface. The actual impact loaded to four points as shown in Figure 5. Identification numbers of the impacts were set as I-1, I-2, I-3 and I-4 sequentially from the right in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Setup of the impact detection of structural elements

In addition, three types of FBGs were located as shown in figure 1, and table 1 shows the brief

description of FBG sensors, which we used as sensors for impact detection. The output port of the AWG filter was selected for the elastic wave acquisition due to detect an impact using most neighboring ports for the center wavelength of the FBG sensor.

Table 1. Sensor for impact detection

No.	Setting condition	Gage length	Diameter
		mm	μm
1	Embedded	1	52
2	Bonded	1	52
3	Bonded	10	250

4 Results and discussions

4.1 Impact detection with flat panels

Figure 6 shows the results of impact damage detection using the FBG/PZT damage monitoring system that we proposed. Figure 7 shows the ultrasonic inspection image acquired by c-scan method and the damage area is approximately 397 mm². After the impact of 19.8 J, the amplitude of the

(a) Input signal of PZT actuator

(b) Received waveforms before and after an impact

Figure 6. Impact damage detection results

received lamb wave was attenuated. Therefore, these results indicate that this damage monitoring system can detect the damage generated by impact.

Fig. 7 Ultrasonic inspection image

From figure 8 to 12 show the results of impact detection using FBG sensor and AWG-type filters. The waveform generated by the impacts having energies ranging from 3.3 to 26.4 J could be successfully received using our damage monitoring system. In case of impact energy level of 3.3 J, 6.7 J and 13.1 J, output voltages were produced in channel 1 and 2. In case of impact energy level of 19.8 J, output voltages were produced in from channel 1 to 3. Moreover, in case of highest energy level of 26.4 J, output voltages were produced in from channel 1 to 4. Namely the number of channels of AWG-type filters that indicate output voltages increases as impact energy level increases. This change of the number of channels is corresponded to a shift of center wavelength of a FBG reflection spectrum. And this shift is corresponded to the strain in grating section of the FBG sensor, therefore the number of channels that indicate output voltages might be able to consider as one of the indexes to detect energy level of the loaded impact. Moreover values of output voltages in each channels might be have correlation to the energy levels of impacts. The change rate of output voltages in channel 1 is considered the biggest in the channels that indicate output in all impact cases and negative output voltages are only indicated in channel 1. On the other hand, the biggest positive output voltage, which is approximately 1.8 V, is indicated in channel 2.

Taking into consideration of mentioned above, these two parameters, namely, the number of

channels that indicate output signals and the value of output voltages, might be very useful indexes to estimate the impact energy when unknown impacts are detected using the FBG/AWG damage monitoring system.

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 1

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 2

Figure 8 Received waveforms by AWG-type Filters at impact energy level of 3.3 J

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 1

Figure 9 Received waveforms by AWG-type Filters at impact energy level of 6.7 J

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 2

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 1

Figure 9. received waveforms by AWG-type filters at impact energy level of 6.7 J (cont.)

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 1

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 2

Figure 10. received waveforms by AWG-type filters at impact energy level of 13.1 J

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 2

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 3

Figure 11. received waveforms by AWG-type filters at impact energy level of 19.8 J

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 1

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 2

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 3

Output of the AWG-type filter channel 4

Figure 12. received waveforms by AWG-type filters at impact energy level of 26.4 J

4.2 Impact detection with structural elements

Figures 13 and 14 show the received waveform and the enlarged figure of the waveform of the elastic wave of FBG sensors No. 2 and No. 3 when the impact positions were changed. All the FBG sensors detected the elastic waves. In particular, FBG sensor No. 3 (normal diameter, gage length: 10 mm) showed the largest output. On the other hand, we compared the performance of the FBG sensor with a small diameter for both the embedded and bonded cases. The output of an embedded FBG sensor showed small signal with a large noise compared to a bonded FBG sensor. However, this is depended on the intensity of the optical source power and the embedded position and conditions. The waveforms generated by the impact showed a complexity in their initial part (0–50 ms) contrasting with the later part (after 50 ms) which showed a regular pattern. Further, waveforms were received by FBG sensors were quite different from the waveforms received by PZT which we used as a trigger of a measurement beginning. It is thought that difference of sensitivity between FBG sensors and PZTs causes the difference of the waveforms. Furthermore, when we change the travel distance of the elastic wave by changing impact location, the amplitudes of the received waveforms are not considerably attenuated. From these test results, it is expected that a long gage and bonded FBG sensor are suitable for impact detection by the abovementioned process.

It is necessary to use the delay in the arrival time of the elastic wave received by more than three FBG sensors and the trigger from the PZT element for the identification of an impact location. In this experiment, in the case of impact location at I-3 in Figure 5, the elastic waves received by the bonded FBG sensor with a small diameter are shown in Figure 7. The wave received by the PZT element is shown in this figure, too. From this figure, it was confirmed that the time difference of approximately 0.34 msec was caused by the delay in the arrival time of the elastic waves between FBG sensor and PZT element. Therefore, the spread speed of the elastic wave was approximately 1.5 km/s because the difference of distance between FBG sensor – impact location and PZT – impact location was 530 mm. However, this calculated speed of elastic wave was somewhat low in comparison with that (A0 wave: 4 km/s, S0 wave: 8 km/s) calculated from the

material stiffness of the specimen. Thus, it was confirmed that identification of impact location was possible by measuring the delay in the arrival time of the received elastic wave, although the properties of elastic wave must be understood precisely.

Figure 13. Output waveform of FBG sensor No. 2 after impact (small/bonded) (Continued)

Figure 13. Output waveform of FBG sensor No. 2 after impact (small/bonded)

Figure 14. Output waveform of FBG sensor No. 3 after impact (standard/bonded)

Figure 14. Output waveform of FBG sensor No. 3 after impact (standard/bonded) (Continued)

Figure 15. Time delay measured by using the elastic wave received by FBG No.

5 Conclusions

Through this study, it was observed that the damage monitoring system using an FBG sensor and AWG-type filter could receive the waves generated by impact which energies range is up to 26.4 J and could also detect the resulting damage. Moreover it is revealed that identification of impact location can be possible to measure the delay in the arrival time of the received elastic wave.

As the result of this study, it was revealed that two kind of detections, damage monitoring and impact detection, with the same system construction by which the damage monitoring using the FBG and PZT hybrid sensor system might be feasible.

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